

Characterization of particle heat carriers for solar particle receivers for pyrolysis application

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ABSTRACT

The use of Particle Heat Carriers (PHCs) for high-temperature heat transfer has attracted growing attention due to their ability to store significant thermal energy, withstand extreme conditions, and ensure efficient heat exchange in applications such as industrial processes and solar reactors. A detailed understanding of PHC properties is crucial for optimizing system performance. This study provides a comprehensive characterization of five widely used PHCs—bauxite, silicon carbide, magnesium oxide, olivine, and sand—focusing on their thermal, mechanical, and chemical properties for biomass pyrolysis applications. A distinctive aspect of this work is the inclusion of biochar in the analysis, offering new insights into its potential as a sustainable heat transfer medium. Results highlight the importance of property-based selection criteria for PHCs and demonstrate the value of systematic evaluation for high-temperature applications. Among the tested materials, bauxite, olivine, and sand emerged as the most suitable candidates, achieving a balanced combination of thermal stability, mechanical strength, and chemical compatibility. Silicon carbide also showed favorable characteristics but suffered from high abrasion. Although biochar offers economic and logistical advantages, its limited mechanical robustness restricts its suitability for this purpose.

Introduction

Biomass pyrolysis is a widely researched process due to the potential of gaining valuable bioproducts like biochar, syngas, and bio-oils, while also promoting the valorization of waste materials. However, pyrolysis is an energy-intensive endothermic process with an enthalpy range between 1.3 and 2 MJ/kg for the case of wood chips as an exemplary feedstock [1]. Furthermore, pyrolysis requires high temperatures, ranging from 300 °C to 900 °C, and often suffers from low profitability. One of the main reasons for low profitability is that a portion of the biochar produced is often consumed as fuel to maintain the necessary temperature, reducing the overall yield. Indeed, Char generally holds around 25 % of the feedstock's energy, with approximately 75 % of that energy needed to sustain the reaction of pyrolysis [2]. In cases where biochar is not used as fuel, the energy required for pyrolysis is supplied by fossil fuels. Among alternative energy resources, solar pyrolysis reactors have been widely developed in recent years [3–5]. The energy

used for these reactors is provided by Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) systems. Solar reactors have already demonstrated their ability to reach high temperatures corresponding to those required for the pyrolysis reaction, but they have several drawbacks. First, the diurnal and intermittent nature of sunlight availability, which implies that it is not always available when needed, makes it impossible to provide a consistent energy source 24 h a day, 7 days a week without having a storage. In the case of solar pyrolysis reactors, the presence of hot spots, the risk of window contamination for a reactor directly irradiated through a window, the optical efficiency, the reactor thermal efficiency, the heat distribution in the pyrolysis reactor and the high cost due to the operation atmosphere are real challenges to consider [6,7].

The European project PYSOLO (PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLar pOwer) [8] seeks to address many of these challenges by introducing Particle Heat Carriers (PHCs) as an intermediate heat source to achieve the required pyrolysis temperatures. The PHCs, which will be heated in a rotary kiln-based solar receiver, allow the pyrolysis reaction

Abbreviations: Cp, Specific heat capacity; CST, Concentrated Solar Thermal; EDX, Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy; MgO, Magnesium Oxide; PHC, Particle Heat Carrier; PYSOLO, PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLar pOwer; SEM, Scanning Electron Microscopy; SiC, Silicon Carbide.

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Fig. 1. Overview of PYSOLO concept [8].

to be decoupled from the solar heat collection and serve as a thermal storage media, enabling 24/7 operation.

The process concept works as follows: when the PHCs have reached a temperature ranging between 600 °C and 800 °C in the solar receiver, they are stored and then injected in the pyrolysis reactor when needed, mixing with the biomass feedstock of choice (for example, pine wood chips). After the pyrolysis reaction is completed, a biochar/PHC separator is used to recover the PHCs, which can be reheated in the solar receiver. A general schematic of the process considered in this project is shown in Fig. 1.

To identify the most suitable PHC candidate for this process, five different PHCs, including bauxite, silicon carbide (SiC), magnesium oxide (MgO), olivine, and sand, were analyzed and characterized. These 5 PHC have been selected since several requirements must be met for the PYSOLO project. First, PHC has to be suitable for recirculation, i.e. good thermal stability and low degree of particle fracture and attrition. The chosen PHC must be available in the size range suitable for a fluidized bed reactor to couple the solar receiver and the pyrolysis unit.

The chosen materials (bauxite, SiC, olivine, sand) have been previously considered for CST applications due to their good thermal resistance or good fracture resistance [9]. In the case of MgO, this material has been included for energy storage applications using CST, and could have interesting synergies with biomass pyrolysis [10]. Although some may act as catalysts, such as MgO or olivine, these materials do not

Table 1

Chemical composition and mean particle diameter for the 5 PHCs.

Composition (%) /	Bauxite	SiC	MgO	Olivine	Sand
SiO ₂	23.5		5	42	99.5
Al ₂ O ₃	76		1	0.4	0.13
Fe ₂ O ₃	≤ 3	0.2	4	7	
MgO			83	50	
CaO			5		
Cr ₂ O ₃				0.3	
NiO				0.3	
SiC		99			
C, free		0.5			
Mean Particle Diameter / μm	250	300	250	250	250

chemically interfere with the pyrolysis reaction and play an inert role. Certain materials such as CaO were initially considered but quickly discarded due to their change in size with each cycle and because of their overly significant role as catalysts in the pyrolysis reaction.

In addition to these five PHCs, biochar derived from pine wood pyrolysis has also been considered as a potential PHC, as it would remove the need for a biochar/PHC separator in the overall process flow. The evaluation focused on a comprehensive range of properties, including thermal, chemical, and mechanical characteristics.

- Thermal properties were assessed to ensure the thermal stability of each PHC at high temperatures and to understand their thermal storage capacity. This is critical for maintaining consistent heat transfer throughout the pyrolysis process.
- Chemical properties were evaluated to check the compatibility between the PHCs and the biomass used in the pyrolysis process, as well as the interaction between the PHCs and the lining material in the solar receiver. These factors are essential for ensuring no undesirable chemical reactions occur that could degrade the system or inhibit the pyrolysis reaction.
- Mechanical properties were analyzed to assess the flowability, as well as the potential abrasiveness to the receiver surface and attrition of the PHCs. Good flowability ensures proper particle flow in the receiver and overall particle flow loop, while minimizing abrasion and attrition is crucial for preventing wear on the receiver walls and the particles themselves, extending its operational lifespan.

Based on these studies, and including the results of our previous work on the optical properties of the same materials [11] a ranking of the different PHCs was established. The two most promising candidates were selected for testing in the next phase of the project. In this next stage, the selected PHCs will be tested in a solar receiver system, utilizing solar energy to heat the particles in the expected operational conditions.

Beyond the PYSOLO project, this work provides a comparative analysis of different PHCs commonly used in current solar research and contributes to a deeper understanding of this field.

Fig. 2. Selected biomass and potential PHCs for pyrolysis reaction (from left to right): wood chips from pine wood, biochar, bauxite, SiC, MgO, olivine and sand.

Table 2
Biomass characterization (wood chips from pine wood).

Type of analysis	Biomass
Proximate analysis (wt. %)	
Moisture	7.04
Volatiles ¹	76.11
Ash	0.58
Fixed Carbon	16.27
Ultimate analysis (wt. %)	
C	46.96
H	6.24
N	0.13
O	46.09
HHV (MJ/kg)	17.91

¹Volatiles matter consists of the gases produced during the initial phase of biomass ignition. For woody biomass it includes mainly CO, CO₂, H₂ and CH₄.

Materials and methods

Material analysis

For the selection of the candidate PHCs, an initial literature review identified 5 well-known and commonly used PHCs: bauxite, silicon carbide (SiC), magnesium oxide (MgO), olivine and silica sand [9,12,13].

To avoid the need for a biochar/PHC separator, and from both an economical and innovative perspective, the PYSOLO project also proposed investigating biochar itself as a potential candidate to serve as the PHC for the pyrolysis reaction. The five PHCs, as well as the pine wood chips selected as the biomass and the resulting biochar, are displayed in Fig. 2.

The chemical composition and average particle size of the five PHCs are presented in Table 1, while the characteristics of the biomass are shown in Table 2. In order to meet the requirements of the pyrolysis reactor [8], samples of each PHC were obtained with a particle size distribution in the range of 100 to 300 μm .

Characterization of the samples

In order to determine which PHC is the most suitable for the PYSOLO process, several analyses were performed on each of the 5 PHCs, as well as on the biochar. Various properties of each PHC were assessed, including mechanical, thermal and chemical.

Mechanical properties. Since the final PHC will be heated in a rotary kiln and subsequently transported through various channels before reaching the pyrolysis reactor, it was essential to assess both the flowability and the abrasiveness of each PHC with potential surface substrates.

Flowability of PHCs. To evaluate the flowability of the PHCs, two tests were conducted: a chute angle test and an angle of repose test.

These tests are widely recognized for contributing to the assessment of the flowability of particles [14] and they served as simple tests for performing a relative comparison of flowability between different PHC materials in this study. The first test aimed to measure the friction between each PHC and an inclined wall by identifying the critical chute angle. A 50 g sample of each PHC was placed on a horizontal steel plate, which was then gradually tilted by a few degrees at a time until the entire sample slid off. The PHCs that fell were collected on a scale positioned at the end of the plate to measure the mass displaced at each angle (Fig. 3a).

These tests were conducted for each PHC, including biochar, at ambient temperature and again after heating in an air atmosphere for 1 h at 950 °C (i.e., the expected highest temperature in the solar receiver due to the presence of hot spots). Due to handling issues, the flowability could not be measured directly after heating but after the PHCs have cooled down. It is important to note, however, that the biochar could not be tested at 950 °C due to combustion safety risks so only tests at room temperature are presented for the biochar. The furnace used to heat the particles was a Carbolite Gero RHF 14/35 in an air atmosphere. A heating rate of 10 °C/min was applied, followed by a 1-hour isothermal hold.

The second test involved measuring the angle of repose. For each PHC, a mass of 50 g was poured through a funnel onto a smooth surface, allowing the material to naturally form a conical pile (Fig. 3b). For the biochar, the initial mass was 5 g due to the much larger volume taken by the biochar compared to the others PHC. The resulting angle of repose was recorded. To assess the impact of temperature, this measurement was performed both at room temperature and after the same heating procedure described above — again, with the exception of biochar, for which only the room temperature measurement was carried out due to the aforementioned safety concerns. For this test, the measure of the angle of repose could be done directly after the heating at 950 °C without any cooling phase of the PHCs.

Each of these two tests was repeated three times to minimize measurement uncertainty and the average value was selected as the final value.

Abrasion resistance of receiver surface with PHCs and attrition of each PHC. In the PYSOLO project (Fig. 1), PHCs are reused several times and are heated in a rotary kiln solar receiver. In this thermocycle, the receiver surface must exhibit high abrasion resistance against falling and sliding particles. For this reason, the abrasion resistance of each PHC with different potential surface materials was a critical characteristic to evaluate.

For an efficient receiver component with longer life time, high abrasion resistance against falling and moving particles plays a crucial role [15–17]. There are several standardized techniques to measure abrasive resistance of components such as: dry sand rubber wheel abrasion test (ASTM G65), high-stress abrasion test (ASTM B611) and wet-sand rubber wheel abrasion test (ASTM G105), gas jet particle impact (ASTM G76-13) [18–20]. In our study, we have assessed

Fig. 3. (a) Friction on an inclined wall with biochar, (b) picture used for the determination of the angle of repose.

resonance acoustic mixer (RAM), where particles were accelerated and collide to the surface of the components, which is similar to the collisions in the real application.

In a typical experiment, 50 g of each PHC was placed into plastic bottles and agitated in a resonance acoustic mixer (model Resodyn LabRam II) with a normal acceleration of 883 m.s^{-2} for 30 min. RAM equipment has distinct acceleration possibilities enabling various agitation conditions from 10 g to 100 g (where “g” represents the g-force). In this study, we have used 80 g, which was employed in the previous parametric study [21] (the maximum limit with this device is 981 m.s^{-2}). Three different substrates were placed on the top of the bottle, which ensured collision of the PHCs with the sample surface, resulting in abrasion related debris formation and weight loss. For details on the method, the reader is referred to [21]. The abrasion resistance of Steel 1.4841, Inconel 2.4816, and Ceramic (SIK-Z) substrate surfaces were examined for each PHC in a comparative manner. These substrate materials were selected as potential candidates for the construction of the solar receiver. The measurements with each substrate and PHC were repeated two times, and the cumulated mass loss was recorded. The abrasion rate is calculated considering the surface area of the substrate,¹ which is exposed to the contact with the particles, and the duration of the two measurements according to Eq. (1).

$$\text{Normalized abrasion rate} = \frac{\frac{\text{cumulative mass loss}}{\text{initial mass}}}{\frac{\text{contact area}}{\text{duration of experiment}}} \quad 1$$

To assess the attrition of each PHC, the particle size distribution before and after each abrasion resistance test were compared, using an electronic sieve shaker from Haver & Boecker model Haver EML 200 Pure Maschine 21271-year 2020 to measure the size distribution.

Thermal properties

Thermogravimetric analysis. For the PYSOLO project (Fig. 1), PHC are reused in a closed-loop system and exposed to temperatures ranging from 400 to 950 °C. Therefore, it was essential to check the thermal stability of each PHC. Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out to measure the mass loss of each PHC over five heating and cooling cycles. The device used for this purpose was a STA 449 F3 Jupiter® from NETZSCH. In the proposed solar-driven pyrolysis reactor, a rotary kiln receiver with an open aperture heats the particles between 600 and 800 °C before transferring the solar heat to the pyrolysis reactor at a temperature between 400 and 500 °C. To simulate these conditions in the thermal stability, a constant flow of synthetic air was injected during each heating phase at 950 °C, while pure nitrogen (N₂) was used for each “cooling phase” at 400 °C. However, if biochar is selected as the PHC for the system, a closed aperture solar receiver operating in an inert atmosphere must be used to avoid combustion of the biochar. Therefore, both the heating and cooling phase were performed under a N₂ atmosphere with biochar.

In each case, a 1-hour isothermal hold was maintained for each heating and cooling cycle, with a heating and cooling rate of 10 K/min employed.

Chemical compatibility

Chemical compatibility with receiver material. The final operating temperature in the solar receiver ranges between 800 °C and 950 °C. It is well known that, at these temperatures, oxidation reactions can occur between steel and oxidative solid samples, potentially producing chromate VI [22–24]. To identify the most suitable PHC and receiver material combination, each PHC was placed in contact with each candidate substrate material and heated with rate of 10 K/min, followed by a 1 h hold at 950 °C (Fig. 4) within a Carbolite Gero RHF 14/35 furnace under

Fig. 4. Ceramic, steel and Inconel samples with different PHC before heating.

an air atmosphere. As a reference for comparison, one substrate sample was heated with no PHC contact under the same conditions.

After heating, the PHCs were removed from the surfaces of the substrates – Steel 1.4841, Inconel 2.4816, SiC G-type – and their surface changes analyzed using a Hitachi High Tech’s SU3900 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) combined with Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The metallic substrate samples (Ø 18 mm) were mounted directly on the Hitachi sample holder (Ø 30 mm) using carbon tapes without Pt-sputtering and the bigger ceramic substrates were cut on their edges using tongs down to 30–50 mm in diameter, which were fixed on the holder of Ø 51 mm and subsequently were sputtered with Platinum to improve its conductivity. To reduce the impact of having substrate samples with different size and a not identical distribution of PHC on the substrate surfaces, the microstructural analyses and elemental mapping were done in the middle of the substrates which were in contact with PHC during the heating.

Chemical compatibility with biomass. Another key aspect of this study was the chemical compatibility between biomass and each PHC. Since the PHCs will be directly mixed with the biomass in the pyrolysis reactor, it was essential to ensure that the selected PHCs act as an inert media and do not interfere with the pyrolysis reaction. To assess this, TGAs were conducted at 500 °C under a N₂ atmosphere to simulate conditions expected in the pyrolysis reactor. A first, TGA of only the biomass was performed as a reference. Then, six additional TGAs were carried out with biomass mixed with one of the PHCs or biochar. The ratio between the biomass and the PHC or biochar was 1:3 with respect to mass to replicate the expected conditions of the pyrolysis reactor.

Results

Mechanical properties

Flowability of PHC

To compare the flowability of the different PHC, the chute angle was measured at ambient temperature and after heating at 950 °C for all PHCs and only at ambient temperature for the biochar. The cumulative mass of material discharged at each angle was recorded and plotted. With each new discharge, the mass that has fallen is added to that of the previous one. Thus, the more significant discharge a PHC has, the higher the cumulative mass will be. Since only significant drops ($\pm 0.5 \text{ g}$) are counted, there can be a significant variation in the number of data between different PHCs. The results are summarized in Fig. 5. The cumulated mass includes the 3 tests performed for each PHC and the biochar.

Results can be interpreted in two ways: firstly, by analyzing the slope of the cumulative mass curve and secondly, by determining the angle at which the plate clears. For instance, although bauxite does not exhibit the steepest slope in the cumulative mass plot, the entire sample flowed at an angle of 24° at room temperature and 26° after heating – indicating very good flowability. This behavior can be attributed to the spherical shape of bauxite particles, in contrast to olivine and SiC which have

¹ This contact area corresponds to the area of a circle with a diameter of 28 mm.

Fig. 5. Results of the chute angle tests for the different PHCs at ambient temperature and after heating and for biochar at ambient temperature.

Fig. 6. Microscopic images with zoom level from x6 to x200 of (a) bauxite, (b) SiC and (c) olivine.

Table 3

Chute angle and angle of repose for every PHC at ambient temperature and after heating at 950 °C and at ambient temperature for biochar.

		Sand	Bauxite	Olivine	SiC	MgO	Biochar
Chute Angle (°)	Ambient Temperature	30.0 ± 2.3	22.2 ± 1.6	29.2 ± 0.7	26.3 ± 0.5	33.4 ± 2.5	35.1 ± 4.2
	950 °C	28.6 ± 2.1	26 ± 1.0	27.8 ± 0.5	29.9 ± 1.7	35.2 ± 3.3	–
Angle of Repose (°)	Ambient Temperature	33.0 ± 0.8	19.3 ± 0.3	36.4 ± 0.8	35.2 ± 1.6	36.2 ± 0.7	45.8 ± 1.4
	950 °C	33.9 ± 0.7	19.8 ± 0.3	34.1 ± 0.9	36.1 ± 1.2	38.4 ± 0.8	–

Fig. 7. Normalized abrasion rate of each PHC for: (a) stainless steel substrate, (b) Inconel substrate, (c) ceramic substrate.

lower sphericity and therefore reduced flow performance. Some microscopic images acquired with a Zeiss Ste REO Discovery V20 optical microscope shown on Fig. 6 illustrate this difference of sphericity.

Biochar showed the poorest flow behavior. It tended to adhere to the test surface and did not flow readily, which significantly hindered accurate measurements.

Heating of the PHC did not appear to significantly affect the flowability. Although a slight variation in the angle at which the entire mass fell was observed after heating, the difference was negligible for all PHCs. A summary of the chute angles can be found in Table 3.

The average values of the three measured angles of repose for each PHC at ambient temperature and after heating are also summarized in Table 3. The corresponding standard deviations are also included.

The tests revealed differences of 2 to 6 % between PHCs at ambient temperature and those heated to 950 °C for the angle of repose and a variation of 6 to 9 % for the chute angle. The diminution of the angle of chute observed for the MgO, SiC and bauxite could be due to particle agglomeration or diminution of moisture content during heating, which increases cohesion and consequently impairs flow [25].

The angle of repose is closely related to the cohesiveness and relative flowability of granular materials. As shown in the work of Shah *et al.*

[26], and according to the classification proposed by Carr, materials with an angle of repose below 30° are considered to have an excellent flowability, angle of repose ranged between 31 and 35° have a good flowability, between 36 and 40°, the flowability is fair and for an angle of repose above 45°, are considered to have poor flowability. Based on this classification, bauxite has an excellent flowability, sand has a good flowability, and olivine, SiC and MgO fall into the category of fair flowability. Biochar, on the other hand, exhibits poor flowability.

This ranking system aligns well with the chute angle test, confirming the observed trends.

Abrasion resistance of receiver surface with PHCs and attrition of each PHC

The abrasion resistance results for each PHC with the different substrate materials are presented in Fig. 7. The difference of normalized mass measured on each substrate reflects the level of abrasion caused by each PHC under the test conditions.

The results indicate that steel and Inconel exhibit relatively low mass loss across all PHCs, suggesting good abrasion resistance. Among the tested PHCs, SiC was the most abrasive when in contact with these two metal substrates. For the result with steel substrate, we can observe a mass gain with MgO samples. This can be linked to some remaining

Fig. 8. SEM image with a zoom x500 of (a) ceramic before abrasion test, (b) ceramic after abrasion test, (c) steel before abrasion test and (d) steel after abrasion test.

Fig. 9. Attrition of PHC before and after abrasion resistance tests with steel and ceramic for (a) Bauxite, (b) SiC, (c) MgO, (d) Olivine and (e) Sand.

particles attached to the steel substrate or can also be attributed to the standard deviation of the scale (0.18 mg). Similarly, The PHC/substrate combinations that show very low abrasion are in the range of the standard deviation of the scale.

In contrast, the ceramic substrate showed significantly higher mass loss (factor of 10 compared to steel and Inconel) with all PHCs, particularly with bauxite, MgO and SiC, indicating a greater sensitivity to abrasion under the test conditions. This might result in different abrasion properties as hardness or toughness which can induce lower abrasion resistance. It was previously reported by Evan et al [27] and afterwards validated by Amini et al. [28] that the effect of hardness in reducing erosion is less than the effect of toughness. Although ceramic substrate (SiC) is way harder than metallic substrates, lack of ductility and toughness may result in our abrasion behaviour. Four samples were

chosen for morphology analyses by using SEM to approve the above statement: SiC-ceramic and steel substrates before and after bauxite abrasion tests. Bauxite was chosen because it shows the most pronounced difference between ceramic and metal substrates. The rough ceramic surface revealed no significant changes in its morphology after abrasive bauxite bombardment, there were only a few bauxite particles sitting on the surface, as shown in the Fig. 8b.

In contrast, the original steel surface showed scratch lines which were changed after abrasion of bauxite particles into to a smooth surface due to its ductile behavior. Bauxite particles are embedded in the surfaces as shown in the Fig. 8d. This indicates that the bombardment with bauxite particles causes predominantly plastic deformation rather than abrasion. Furthermore, the embedded remainders of bauxite particles increase the mass of the sample, counteracting mass losses due to

Fig. 10. 5-cycle TGA under synthetic air atmosphere at 950 °C and under N₂ atmosphere at 400 °C for bauxite, SiC, MgO, olivine and sand.

Fig. 11. 5-cycle TGA under N₂ atmosphere at 950 °C and 400 °C for biochar.

abrasion.

In the case of the choice of ceramic as the final material for the reactor surface, a coating layer could be added to reduce the abrasion resistance. Nevertheless, it is important to remind that these tests were performed under extreme condition to compare the different materials substrate and is not a standard test to obtain abrasion resistance value. For the experimental campaign, we expect less abrasion resistance. For this reason, this analysis should be seen more as a qualitative comparison between steel, Inconel and ceramic.

The attrition results are shown in Fig. 9. Since results obtained with steel and Inconel were very similar, only results with steel are presented here. Attrition tests were not performed with biochar, as the sieves size were not appropriate for the size of the biochar particles.

Table 4

SEM EDX results for Steel with the different PHC. Results are presented as a percent weight.

	O	C	Si	Mg	Al	N	V	Ti	Mn	Cr	Fe	Ni
Ambient temperature without PHC		0.2	1.5–2.5						2	24–26	47.1–55	19–22
Heated at 950 °C without PHC	25.2	4.95	0.2	–	–	–	–	–	8.6	55.1	6.5	2
MgO	27.5	–	0.88	–	–	–	–	–	10.21	52.81	5.62	2.06
SiC	24.97	3.32	1.36	–	–	–	–	–	3.33	25.48	34.76	5.35
Bauxite	25.68	2.89	0.85	–	–	–	–	–	8.16	49.71	8.55	2.66
Olivine	27.14	–	0.5	–	–	–	–	–	9.48	57.61	4.26	1
Sand	26.83	–	0.87	–	–	–	–	–	8.69	55.83	6.42	1.37

Results show that the particle size distribution has not been significantly impacted by the agitation experienced in the abrasion resistance tests for any PHC-substrate combination. MgO is the PHC for which this test had the highest impact, while SiC demonstrated no observable change in the particle size distribution. These results indicate very low attrition for each of these PHCs, which is a benefit to the PYSOLO process, as particles can be continuously recycled for a longer time before requiring replacement. Regardless of the PHC material chosen for the solar receiver, these tests show that any PHC is suitable from this respect.

Thermal properties

Thermogravimetric analysis

The TGA results over five thermal cycles for bauxite, SiC, MgO, olivine and sand and are presented in Fig. 10 and results for biochar are shown in Fig. 11.

The mass loss observed for bauxite, olivine, sand and SiC remained highly stable and below 1% throughout the five cycles, indicating good thermal stability. In contrast, MgO showed an initial mass loss of 3.7% during the first cycle, then remained approximately constant.

The initial mass loss of 3.7% in MgO is mainly attributed to the release of volatile species associated with the measured loss on ignition (LOI of 2% from the technical data). The remaining mass loss of 1.7% can result to the partial reduction of Fe₂O₃ (corresponding to 4% of the initial composition of the MgO sample, Table 1) that starts at 600 °C and to the progressive desorption of adsorbed water on MgO or CaO (respectively corresponding to 83 and 5% of the initial composition of the MgO sample, Table 1).

The results for biochar show a significant mass loss of 22% after the first cycle followed by a steady, gradual decrease in mass over the next four cycles until reaching a total mass loss of 25%. The initial biochar was produced through the pyrolysis of pine wood at 500–600 °C, meaning it may still contain residual oxygen and hydrogen which could be released at 950 °C. For the PYSOLO project, this thermal instability is not a real concern since fresh biochar will be produced after each pyrolysis step but this implies using a fraction of new biochar for every cycle, limiting the use of the biochar as a valuable product.

Chemical compatibility properties

Chemical compatibility with receiver material

SEM-EDX analysis for the different substrate materials and each PHC are presented in Tables 4–6.

The SEM images and elemental EDX mapping reveal the heterogeneity in surface morphologies and elemental distribution after heat treatment in air.

As an example, Fig. 12 shows the elemental mapping for Silicon, Oxygen and Carbon for the piece of ceramic in contact with MgO.

Tables 4–6 list the identified elements on the surface and their semi-quantitative amounts for each PHC, in comparison with the reference substrate (at ambient temperature and after heat treatment). Before having a deeper look on these results, it is important to mention that each number is calculated from an elemental mapping of a small piece of the studied material. Since the substrate surfaces are rough and no

Table 5
SEM EDX results for Inconel 600 with the different PHC. Results are presented as a percent weight.

	O	C	Si	Mg	Al	N	V	Ti	Mn	Cr	Fe	Ni
Ambient temperature without PHC	–	<0.1	<0.5	–	<0.3	–	–	<0.3	1	14–17	6–10	72
Heated at 950 °C without PHC	24.6	2.6	0.4	–	0.5	16	–	1.6	–	48.4	2.9	16
MgO	20.08	3.21	1.77	1.27	0.93	–	–	1.38	1.94	24.99	6.37	38.07
SiC	23.56	1.97	0.81	–	0.4	8.66	1.46	0.73	1.15	42.50	3.5	14.37
Bauxite	24.69	3.62	0.96	0.31	1.30	–	–	1.24	1.28	40.20	3.91	22.49
Olivine	31.72	4.90	3.0	–	1.06	–	–	1.59	1.85	37.82	2.95	15.10
Sand	26.54	2.95	1.17	0.20	0.82	–	–	0.98	1.41	44.41	3.19	18.41

Table 6
SEM EDX results for Ceramic with the different PHC. Results are presented as a percent weight.

	O	C	Si	Mg	Al	N	V	Ti	Mn	Cr	Fe	Ni
Ambient temperature without PHC	–	26.4	72.6	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Heated at 950 °C without PHC	13.8	7.4	53.5	–	2.9	16.6	–	–	–	–	–	–
MgO	40	6	48	–	4	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
SiC	8	20	45	–	1	26	–	–	–	–	–	–
Bauxite	21	6	43	–	10	20	–	–	–	–	–	–
Olivine	40	6	49	–	6	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Sand	43	4.3	44	–	8.7	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

Fig. 12. Elemental mapping of (a) Silicon, (b) Oxygen, (c) Carbon for ceramic piece in contact with MgO.

calibration standards were used, the obtained elemental concentrations provide only a qualitative information on corrosion behavior, such as relative oxide layer thickness compared to the pure substrate or reactions of the PHC with the substrate or its thermally grown oxide layer. Especially the calculated fractions of the light elements C, N, and O are highly affected by surface roughness and large errors are expected for the respective values.

In the case of thin oxide layers, the electron beam partially penetrates the oxide layer; therefore, the maps and spectra reflect signals from both the oxide layer and the underlying substrate. The weaker the signal from the substrate, the thicker the oxide layer. If the substrate is compatible with the PHC, the difference in elemental concentrations between the reference and the corresponding PHC should be small. Conversely, significant differences indicate a different corrosion behavior and thus poor compatibility. This can be clearly seen in the case of the Fe and Ni signals of the steel substrate (Table 4). The calculated fractions of these elements, which are not expected to be present in the thermally grown oxide layer, do not vary much for the plain substrate and the different PHC with the exception of SiC, where a much thinner oxide layer is present. Thus, all PHC except SiC are compatible with the steel substrate.

In the case of Inconel substrates, the calculated Fe and Ni fractions are similar for the plain substrate and all PHC except MgO and potentially bauxite. Thus, SiC, sand and olivine appear as suitable PHC in combination with Inconel.

For the analysis of ceramic substrates, one needs to take into account that some of the PHC (SiC, sand and olivine) also contain silicon, which cannot be used as a marker element such as Fe or Ni in the case of metal

substrates. The plain ceramic substrate seems to form a double layer consisting of SiO₂ and Si₃N₄ upon heat treatment in air. This behavior is also observed for SiC and bauxite PHC, but the latter leads to an increased Al content. The other PHC tend to promote growth of SiO₂, where olivine and sand also increase the Al content on the substrate surface. Thus, SiC can be regarded as optimal, self-compatible PHC (the substrate is also SiC-based), while MgO is also suitable as no foreign elements are introduced into the surface layers.

The most suitable PHCs are MgO and bauxite for steel substrates; bauxite and SiC for Inconel; and for ceramic substrates, all tested materials can be considered compatible, with SiC showing particularly good self-compatibility.

With regard to the initial concern about the potential increase in chromium, we can see that this trend is present in steel and Inconel as soon as heat treatment takes place and without the presence of PHC. However, this increase may be linked to the appearance of oxides on the surface of the material, which may turn out to be non-harmful for human health (as Cr₂O₃ or FeCr₂O₄). To rule out the presence of potentially dangerous compound as Sodium chromate or Potassium chromate, other experiments will be necessary. One first option could be the analysis of a side cut area of the steel and Inconel samples to estimate the composition and depth of the oxide layer. A second option could be the dissolution of the chromate in the water and analyze the solution using ion chromatography or test with silver nitrate.

Chemical compatibility with biomass

The TGA results at 500 °C in a N₂ atmosphere for only biomass and biomass mixed with the different PHCs (using a mass ratio of biomass-to-

Fig. 13. TGA results for biomass and biomass mixed with the different PHCs at 500 °C in a N₂ atmosphere.

Fig. 14. TGA results for biomass and biomass mixed with biochar at 500 °C in a N₂ atmosphere.

PHC of 1:3) are shown in Fig. 13. The plot for biomass mixed with MgO has been corrected to account for the mass loss of MgO at 500 °C, such that the results presented in Fig. 13 present only the mass loss of the biomass and not the total combined mass loss of the PHC + biomass.

The TGA results at 500 °C in N₂ atmosphere for only biomass and biomass mixed with biochar (again, using a biomass-to-biochar ratio of 1:3) are presented in Fig. 14. This plot has also been corrected considering the mass loss of the biochar at 500 °C.

The TGA results for biomass mixed with PHC show no significant difference in mass loss (a maximum of 2 %-pts variation) compared to pure biomass (Fig. 12). This result confirms that the PHCs play an inert role and do not influence the pyrolysis reaction at the tested conditions. For the TGA of biomass mixed with biochar (Fig. 13), a mass loss difference of 4 %-pts was observed for the biomass/biochar mixture compared to the biomass alone.

Although it is true that several studies have shown that the presence of inorganic components in the biochar structure can have a catalytic effect on the pyrolysis process [29–31], this effect usually happens at temperatures greater than 500 °C (starting from 600 °C). For a reaction at 500 °C, it has been shown that biochar also plays an inert role in the pyrolysis reaction at TGA condition and could be mixed with biomass in the pyrolysis reactor.

Other aspects

In addition to the various analyses described in the previous sections, additional factors were also considered for the final selection of the PHC most suitable for the PYSOLO solar-driven pyrolysis reactor.

Optical properties

Solar absorptance and infrared thermal emittance of the evaluated PHCs are key factors in the absorptance and retention of solar energy in the solar receiver and heat release in the pyrolysis reactor. In our previous study [11] we determined these properties for each of the PHCs by measuring the reflectance of the PHC at room temperature. Both properties were calculated considering the state of the PHCs at 4 different conditions: i) as received materials, ii) after heating in a furnace under air at 950 °C (simulating the status after heating in the solar receiver), iii) after pyrolysis at 800 °C under N₂ atmosphere, and iv) after heating in a furnace with air at 950 °C for PHCs post-pyrolysis (to simulate the cyclic nature of the PHC cycle, whereby particles return to the solar receiver after pyrolysis and separation from the biochar).

The absorptance and emittance of olivine, sand and MgO demonstrated significant changes linked to the process conditions. For all conditions tested, SiC and bauxite had high absorptance and emittance (more than 90 % and 88 % respectively). Detail information about the measurement procedure and the results for each condition is described in [11].

Receiver design

As previously mentioned, the PHC will be heated in a rotary kiln-based solar receiver. A receiver with an open aperture is desired, as it simplifies design aspects and the overall operation. However, for tests involving biochar, a closed configuration will be necessary due to the risk of combustion or gasification of the biochar at high temperatures in the presence of air. For a solar receiver, the closed configuration can be implemented in two ways:

- Direct irradiation through an aperture window
- Indirect irradiation through the receiver wall surface

Both configurations present significant technical challenges. A window must be kept clean to ensure solar irradiation penetrates into the receiver, which is particularly difficult with materials, such as biochar, which generate considerable dust. On the other hand, indirect irradiation leads to higher heat losses than direct irradiation and achieving the required temperature range of 600 to 800 °C with an indirect system is more challenging. The PYSOLO project aims for a thermal efficiency of 70–80 % and the selection of biochar as the final PHC choice presents very considerable challenges when taking design considerations into account.

Soil compatibility of PHCs for fertilizer application

The PYSOLO project includes a PHC/biochar separator after the pyrolysis step for two reasons:

- To recover the PHC to be reused in the solar receiver
- To isolate the biochar for utilization as a fertilizer

The efficiency of the separation process will depend on the final PHC selected, but it is unrealistic to expect 100 % separation efficiency. This means that some residual PHC will remain mixed with the biochar. For this reason, it is crucial to assess whether the PHC interfere with the fertilizer properties of the resulting biochar and whether it could pose risks to soil quality. Initial findings suggest that certain materials such as bauxite, due to its high alkalinity and salinity, may have limited suitability for soils application [32]. In contrast, olivine and MgO have excellent impacts on soil and plants, including on plant growth, nutrients, and promotion of photodegradation [33,34]. Other studies have

Table 7
Availability and price of the different PHCs and biochar [9,27–30].

	Tons of PHC available in the world for the year 2020	Price in \$/ton
Biochar	In this case, directly accessible from pyrolysis reaction	Not applicable in this case since it is an output product of pyrolysis
Bauxite	401 500 000	400
SiC	Very rare natural occurrence	1900
MgO	15 180 000	1750–2000
Olivine	160 000 000 in 2024	175
Sand	2 437 000 000 (Europe)	75

Fig. 15. Comparison of the ZBS model with experimental data from literature.

demonstrated the harmful effect of SiC on soil-dwelling earthworms [35]. Therefore, the potential use of bauxite and SiC will be carefully evaluated in relation to the separation efficiency of the particle/char separator and to the specific use cases.

Economic and availability considerations

A final consideration is the cost and availability of each PHC. Indeed, the economic aspect directly influences the feasibility of the process in the long term. Even if a PHC demonstrates better mechanical, thermal, optical or chemical performances, its practical application might be limited if it is prohibitively expensive. The availability of each PHC also plays an important role. Materials that are difficult to source or rarely found as natural can lead to supply chain disruptions, delays in production and finally also increase overall costs. In order to envision the process on a large scale, the material availability should then be ensured. Table 7 summarizes the availability and cost of the materials considered in this study.

Other thermal properties

In addition to TGA, other thermal properties, such as bulk thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity, are relevant parameters for this study. Indeed, as a PHC, it was essential to verify their capacity to store and efficiently transmit the heat stored during mixing with biomass in the pyrolysis reactor. The bulk thermal conductivity of each PHC at 800 °C has been compared using data from the literature and the analytic effective thermal conductivity model of Zehner, Bauer, and Schlünder (ZBS). The ZBS model is a popular model for predicting the thermal conductivity of particle beds and depends on various material properties of the particle material and the interstitial gas (including thermal conductivity, emissivity, particle diameter, molar mass, etc.) and bed void fraction. A reprint from van Antwerpen et al. [36] of the

Fig. 16. Bulk thermal conductivity calculated from ZBS model for MgO, Bauxite, SiC, Sand and Olivine.

Table 8

Specific heat capacity, density and Volumetric heat capacity of the different PHCs and biochar [9,41].

	Specific heat capacity [kJ/(kg.K)] at 800°	Density [g/cm ³]	Volumetric heat capacity [kJ/(m ³ .K)]
Biochar	1.35	0.2–0.5	270–675
Bauxite	1.05	3.5	3675
SiC	1.05	3.2	3360
MgO	1.25	3.25	3675
Olivine	1.25	3.3	4125
Sand	0.95	2.6	2470

original model was used in the calculations here. Before applying the model to the PHCs considered in this work, the ZBS model was first validated by comparing with experimental data from the literature for bauxite [37], silica sand [38], MgO [39], and SiC [40] of similar particle diameters to the PHCs. As seen in Fig. 15, the ZBS model agrees well with the experimental data. The ZBS model was then implemented to predict the bulk thermal conductivity for the PHCs studied here, assuming a void fraction of 0.43 for all PHCs, as measured in other works (Fig. 16) (example, [37]). It can be observed that MgO is the PHC with the highest thermal conductivity, followed by SiC and bauxite/silica sand. While experimental measurements were originally targeted within the scope of this work, a device was not readily available for this purpose. Therefore, to avoid spending additional time and resources for work that several other researchers have previously conducted for similar materials, this combined analysis using modeling and data from literature was deemed acceptable within the scope of the PHC selection process undertaken here.

The volumetric heat capacity of each PHC has been compared using data from suppliers and literature (Table 8). For a particle bed, the specific heat capacity is approximately equal to the specific heat capacity of the particle material, as the thermal mass of the bed is dominated by the solid particles, due to a significantly higher density than the interstitial air. Therefore, data for the particle material is an appropriate representation for the particle bed. Biochar is the PHC with the lowest volumetric heat capacity, thereby necessitating high quantities of biochar compared with the other PHCs. The PHCs with the highest volumetric heat capacity are bauxite, olivine and MgO.

Table 9

Summary of characterization results for bauxite, olivine, sand, SiC, MgO and biochar.

	Bauxite	Olivine	Sand	SiC	MgO	Biochar
Flowability	+++	++	++	++	+	–
Abrasiveness	+++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++
Attrition	+++	+++	+++	++	+++	
Thermal stability	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	–
Volumetric heat capacity	++	++	+	+	++	–
Conductivity	++	++	++	++	+++	++
Chemical compatibility with materials	++	+	+	++	+	
Chemical compatibility with biomass	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
Fertilizer aspects for soil compatibility	–	++	+	--	++	++
Price and availability	++	++	++	+	+	+++
Receiver design considerations						–
Sum of (++++)	5	4	4	2	4	3
Sum of (+++)	4	5	3	5	3	2
Sum of (++)	0	1	3	2	3	0
Sum of (+)	1	0	0	0	0	4
Sum of (–)	0	0	0	1	0	0

Conclusion

This paper provides a comprehensive experimental evaluation of five particle heat carriers (PHCs) and biochar derived from pine wood for solar-driven biomass pyrolysis within the PYSOLO project. A multi-criteria scoring approach was applied to assess their thermal, mechanical and chemical performance under relevant operating conditions. A complete overview of the results is presented in Table 9. In this table, each parameter was given a score based on their perceived benefit for the PYSOLO process: three plus signs (+++) indicates that a property was viewed as excellent, two plus signs (++) as good, one plus sign (+) as satisfactory, a negative sign (–) as unsatisfactory and two negative signs (--) as detrimental.

Based on this analysis, bauxite, olivine, and sand were identified as the most suitable candidates. Although sand and MgO achieved similar overall scores, sand was favored due to its superior thermal stability and flowability. The applicability of bauxite remains dependent on the efficiency of the particle–char separation system.

Despite its environmental advantages, biochar exhibits several limitations, including poor flowability, low thermal conductivity, and design constraints related to receiver configuration, which currently restrict its use as a primary heat carrier.

Additional factors, such as density differences in fluidized bed reactors and potential scale effects, must be considered before final material selection. While TGA results indicate inert behavior at laboratory scale, further validation under pilot scale conditions is required.

Overall, this work establishes a robust experimental framework and a reference dataset for heat carrier selection, in their initial state but also after being subjected to high temperature (from 400 to 950 °C), in different atmospheres (inert or under air) providing valuable guidance for the development and optimization of solar-driven pyrolysis systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Clarisse. Lorreyte: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Matteo. Josse:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Juan. Pablo. Rincon Duarte:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Megan Kirschmeier:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Lamark de Oliveira:** . **Gözde Alkan:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Enkhtsetseg Dashjav:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Martin Roeb:**

Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] Daugaard DE, Brown RC. Enthalpy for Pyrolysis for Several Types of Biomass. *Energy Fuels* 2003;17(4):934–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ef020260x>.
- [2] Bridgwater AV. The production of biofuels and renewable chemicals by fast pyrolysis of biomass. *Int J Global Energy Issues* 2007;27(2):160. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJGEI.2007.013654>.
- [3] Zeng K, Gauthier D, Soria J, Mazza G, Flamant G. Solar pyrolysis of carbonaceous feedstocks: a review. *Sol Energy* 2017;156:73–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.05.033>.
- [4] Ndukwu MC, Horsfall IT, Ubouh EA, Orji FN, Ekop IE, Ezejiofor NR. Review of solar-biomass pyrolysis systems: Focus on the configuration of thermal-solar systems and reactor orientation. *Journal of King Saud University - Engineering Sciences* 2021;33(6):413–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksues.2020.05.004>.
- [5] Mohammad G. Rasul, Abul kalam Azad and Subhash C. Sharma, Ed., *Clean Energy for Sustainable Development*: Elsevier, 2017.
- [6] Maytorena VM, Buentello-Montoya DA. Worldwide developments and challenges for solar pyrolysis. *Heliyon* 2024;10(15):e35464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e35464>.
- [7] Li R, et al. Comparative study of process simulation, energy and exergy analyses of solar enhanced char-cycling biomass pyrolysis process. *Energ Conver Manage* 2024;302:118082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118082>.
- [8] Horizon Europe Project PYSOLO, <https://pysolo.eu/>.
- [9] Kang Q, Flamant G, Dewil R, Baeyens J, Zhang HL, Deng YM. Particles in a circulation loop for solar energy capture and storage. *Particuology* 2019;43:149–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2018.01.009>.
- [10] Stefanidis SD, et al. Natural magnesium oxide (MgO) catalysts: a cost-effective sustainable alternative to acid zeolites for the in situ upgrading of biomass fast pyrolysis oil. *Appl Catal B* 2016;196:155–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2016.05.031>.
- [11] J. P. Rincon Duarte et al., “Solar Absorbance and Thermal Emittance of Particle Heat Carriers in a Solar Driven Biomass Process,” in *Solar Absorbance and Thermal Emittance of Particle Heat Carriers in a Solar Driven Biomass Process* ASME 2025 19th International Conference on Energy Sustainability, Westminster, Colorado, USA, 2025.
- [12] Kim Y, et al. Ultrahigh-Porosity MgO Microparticles for Heat-Energy Storage. *Adv Mater* 2023;35(43):e2204775. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202204775>.
- [13] Daugaard TJ, Dalluge DL, Brown RC, Wright MM. Effect of thermophysical properties of heat carriers on performance of a laboratory-scale auger pyrolyzer. *Fuel Process Technol* 2018;176:182–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2018.03.024>.
- [14] Cheng Z, et al. Flow behavior characterization of biomass Feedstocks. *Powder Technol* 2021;387:156–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2021.04.004>.
- [15] Melentiev R. Physical theories of solid particle erosion and abrasive jet wear. *J Manuf Process* 2023;106:422–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2023.10.014>.
- [16] An W, Yang S, Wen Z, Pan H, Hu H, Zheng Y. A Review: Factors Controlling erosion Resistance in Metals Prioritizing the Influence of Material Mechanics and the

- Related erosion Models. *Metals* 2025;15(11):1177. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met15111177>.
- [17] T. Deng, "Erosive Wear Mechanisms of Materials-A Review of Understanding and Progresses," *Materials*, vol. 18, no. 7, 2025, doi: 10.3390/ma18071615.
- [18] J. Kübarsepp, K. Juhani, and M. Tarraste, "Abrasion and Erosion Resistance of Cermets: A Review," *Materials*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.3390/ma15010069.
- [19] M. Mohagheghi, A. Davodiroknabadi, S. Zohoori, and S. Nayebzadeh, "Fabrication of Novel Acid-Resistant Ceramic With High Abrasion and Flexural Strength Resistance," *Int J Ceramic Engine & Sci*, vol. 7, no. 6, 2025, doi: 10.1002/ces2.70030.
- [20] Dauber C, Vannucchi de Camargo F, Alves AK, Pavlovic A, Fragassa C, Bergmann CP. Erosion resistance of engineering ceramics and comparative assessment through Wiederhorn and Evans equations. *Wear* 2019;432-433: 202938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2019.202938>.
- [21] Mechnich P, Alkan G. Rapid evaluation of the particle-erosion resistance of Al 2 O 3 ceramics, composites, and coatings using a resonant acoustic mixer. *Advances in Applied Ceramics: Structural, Functional and Bioceramics* 2023;122(3-4):250-7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17436753.2023.2231230>.
- [22] Lorreyte, Clarisse and Parmaksiz, Hazal and Lachmann, Bruno and Tesdari, Stefania and Oliveira, Lamark de and Palhares, Dayana D'Arc de Fatima and Moumin, Gkiokchan and Rincon Duarte, Juan Pablo and Fend, Thomas and Roeb, Martin and Sattler, Christian, Ed., *Experimental Study of a Lab Scale Carbonator for CO2 Capture Purpose ASME 2024 18th International Conference on Energy Sustainability: American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, 2024.
- [23] Wood GC. The oxidation of iron-chromium alloys and stainless steels at high temperatures. *Corros Sci* 1962;2(3):173-96. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-938X\(62\)90019-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-938X(62)90019-7).
- [24] S. Hallström, M. Halvarsson, L. Höglund, T. Jonsson, and J. Ågren, "High temperature oxidation of chromium: Kinetic modeling and microstructural investigation," *Solid Oxide Fuel Cells dedicated to Prof. H. Tagawa*, vol. 240, pp. 41-50, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.ssi.2013.02.017.
- [25] Kalman H. Quantification of mechanisms governing the angle of repose, angle of tilting, and Hausner ratio to estimate the flowability of particulate materials. *Powder Technol* 2021;382:573-93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2021.01.012>.
- [26] Shah DS, Moravkar KK, Jha DK, Lonkar V, Amin PD, Chalikwar SS. A concise summary of powder processing methodologies for flow enhancement. *Heliyon* 2023;9(6):e16498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16498>.
- [27] A. G. Evans, M. E. Gulden, and M. Rosenblatt, "Impact damage in brittle materials in the elastic-plastic response régime," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, vol. 361, no. 1706, pp. 343-365, 1978, doi: 10.1098/rspa.1978.0106.
- [28] Garmeh B, Amini K. Comparison between Quench Tempering and Quasi Quench Partitioning Treatment on Structure and Mechanical Properties of Cr-Mo Steel. *Mater Perform Charact* 2019;8(2):297-304. <https://doi.org/10.1520/MPC20180070>.
- [29] Cao X, Sun S, Sun R. Application of biochar-based catalysts in biomass upgrading: a review. *RSC Adv* 2017;7(77):48793-805. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7RA09307A>.
- [30] Lei H, Ren S, Julson J. The Effects of Reaction Temperature and Time and Particle size of Corn Stover on Microwave Pyrolysis. *Energy Fuels* 2009;23(6):3254-61. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ef9000264>.
- [31] Ren S, Lei H, Wang L, Bu Q, Chen S, Wu J. Hydrocarbon and hydrogen-rich syngas production by biomass catalytic pyrolysis and bio-oil upgrading over biochar catalysts. *RSC Adv* 2014;4(21):10731-7. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4RA00122B>.
- [32] Miura YS, Mulder J, Zivanovic V, Courtney R, Okkenhaug G. Enhancing bauxite residue properties for plant growth: Gypsum and organic amendment effects on chemical properties of soil and leachate. *J Environ Manage* 2023;337:117721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117721>.
- [33] Silva AA, Sousa AMF, Furtado CR, Carvalho NM. Green magnesium oxide prepared by plant extracts: synthesis, properties and applications. *Mater Today Sustainability* 2022;20:100203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtsust.2022.100203>.
- [34] ten Berge HFM, van der Meer HG, Steenhuizen JW, Goedhart PW, Knops P, Verhagen J. Olivine weathering in soil, and its effects on growth and nutrient uptake in Ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.): a pot experiment. *PLoS One* 2012;7(8): e42098. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0042098>.
- [35] Al BANNA L. Impact of silicon carbide nanoparticles on hatching and survival of soil nematodes *caenorhabditis elegans* and *meloidogyne incognita*. *Appl Ecol Env Res* 2018;16(3):2651-62. https://doi.org/10.15666/aeer/1603_26512662.
- [36] van Antwerpen W, Du Toit CG, Rousseau PG. A review of correlations to model the packing structure and effective thermal conductivity in packed beds of mono-sized spherical particles. *Nucl Eng Des* 2010;240(7):1803-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2010.03.009>.
- [37] Chung KM, et al. Measurement and analysis of thermal conductivity of ceramic particle beds for solar thermal energy storage. *Sol Energy Mater Sol Cells* 2021; 230:111271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111271>.
- [38] J. Maskalunas, G. Nellis, and M. Anderson, "High-temperature thermal properties of particles in consideration for thermal storage in concentrated solar power systems," in *SOLARPACES 2020: 26th International Conference on Concentrating Solar Power and Chemical Energy Systems*, Freiburg, Germany, 2022, p. 160010.
- [39] Godbee HW, Ziegler WT. Thermal Conductivities of MgO, Al2O3, and ZrO2 Powders to 850° C. I. Experimental. *J Appl Phys* 1966;37(1):40-55. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1707849>.
- [40] Sang L, Wang K, Zhang R, Wang Y, Wu Y. Effective thermal conductivity and thermal cycling stability of solid particles for sCO2 CSP applications. *Sol Energy Mater Sol Cells* 2022;242:111764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2022.111764>.
- [41] Thomas C. Allison, "NIST-JANAF Thermochemical Tables - SRD 13," 2013. 10.18434/T42S31.